

Visualization of Searching and Sorting Algorithms

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Abstract—Sequences of execution of algorithms in an interactive manner using multimedia tools are employed in this paper. It helps to realize the concept of fundamentals of algorithms such as searching and sorting method in a simple manner. Visualization gains more attention than theoretical study and it is an easy way of learning process. We propose methods for finding runtime sequence of each algorithm in an interactive way and aims to overcome the drawbacks of the existing character systems. System illustrates each and every step clearly using text and animation. Comparisons of its time complexity have been carried out and results show that our approach provides better perceptiveness of algorithms.

Keywords—Algorithms, Searching, Sorting, Visualization.

I. INTRODUCTION

VISUALIZATION of algorithms' sequence is an important process to learn various hidden steps, which are involved dynamically. The advantages of visualizing algorithms are: Easy to learn with different set data, Understand hidden steps of algorithms, Memory usages and Time management strategy. The first well-known visualization presented by Baecker, it was in videotape format. It shows the animation of nine different sorting algorithms. This videotape allows students to watch the behavior of the algorithm rather than try to imagine its actions from a verbal explanation or from several static images [1]. *Brown Algorithm Simulator and Animator (BALSA)* is a major interactive algorithm animation system developed at Brown University [2]. In this system Students were able to control the animation by starting, stopping and replaying the animations. A later version *BALSA-II* added color and some rudimentary sounds. Brown University created another algorithm animation system. It does not erase and redraw each image as the previous animation systems did. It is able to produce smoother more cartoon-like animations. A later version of this system is XTANGO[3]. *A New Interactive Modeler for Animations in Lectures (ANIMAL)* is a newer visualization system incorporating lessons learned from pedagogical research Developed at the University of Siegen in Germany [4]. In this paper, some of searching and sorting algorithms

are explained visually. Interaction with this tool can be achieved through the exploration of existing default visualizations, through the direct manipulation of graphics objects. This tool is designed for three different groups of users such as students, instructors and software developers. This will be very interactive which means the user verifies the algorithms by different set of data. We explain the following algorithms in this paper.

Searching Algorithms:

- 1) Sequential Search
- 2) Binary Search
- 3) Interpolation Search

Sorting Algorithms:

- 1) Selection Sort
- 2) Bubble Sort
- 3) Shell Sort

Section 2 describes visualization of searching algorithms and Sorting algorithms have been discussed in section 3. Section 4 deals result and analysis of both kinds of algorithms. Finally, concluding remarks and future enhancements are described in section 5.

II. VISUALIZING SEARCHING TECHNIQUES

Interaction with our system can be achieved through the exploration of existing default visualizations, through the direct manipulation of graphical objects. This will provide the way by selection of concepts (Searching or Sorting) which we want and also select the algorithm based on the selected concept. The inputs for the selected algorithm are obtained from the user. Visualization process starts by clicking the start button. The Buttons Pause and Resume are used to suspend and resume the process of visualization. In both Searching and sorting algorithms, an appropriate message is displayed for each process. In Searching algorithms, when process starts, the component (labels) that contains the element to be searched moves through the list based on the selected algorithm until a match is found. In sorting algorithms, when process starts, the positions of the components (labels) that contain the elements to be sorted are interchanged. This process continues until all the elements are sorted. It contains the following algorithms.

A. Sequential Search

In searching algorithms, the user has to give how many number of input, the set of data and a number to be searched. Then select the particular algorithm from the list and then the

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visualization of the selected algorithm is shown with the given inputs. A Sequential search is one of a search method, also known as linear search that is suitable for searching a list of data with a particular value. It operates by checking every element of a list one at a time in a sequential order until a match is found.

Algorithm Sequential Search (List, Target, N)

List -the elements to be searched

Target -the value being searched for

N -the number of elements in the list

pos -the value of the position from where repaint starts

```

Step1: calls ct.d() //function that starts the timer
Step2: For i=1 to N do
Step3: if (Target=List[i]) then
Step4: Stop the program
Step5: End if
Step6: pos= i//stores the position
Step7: call repaint();
// It moves searching element through out the list
// until a match is found
Step8: End for
Step9: calls ct.d1() //function that stops the timer
    
```

Fig.1 illustrates choosing the algorithm from the given list. Timer is started with the algorithm using the function *ct.d()*. The element to be searched is called the *Target*. For elements 1 to *n* the *Target* is compared with the elements in the *List* starting from the first element. In each step the index value of the element in the *List* with which the *Target* is compared is stored in variable *pos*.

Fig. 1 Sequential search- Choosing the algorithm

Then *repaint()* function is called to move the element to the next position of the *List* as depicted in Fig.2.

Fig. 2 Compares second element with the target

When the *Target* matches with the element of the *List* the program stops as shown in Fig.3 and timer is stopped by calling the function *ct.d1()*.

Fig. 3 Sequential search - Compares third element with the target and match is found

B. Binary Search

In binary search, we first compare the target with the element in the middle position of the array. If there's a match, we can return immediately. If the target is less than the middle element, then the target must lie in the lower half of the array; if the target is greater than the middle element then target must lie in the upper half of the array. So we repeat the procedure on the lower (or upper) half of the array.

Algorithm Binary Search (List, Target, N)

List -the elements to be searched

Target -the value being searched for

N -the number of elements in the list

pos -the value of the position from where repaint starts

thread_var -variable to control the movement of the labels to be exchanged

```

Step1: calls ct.d()//function that starts the timer
Step2: start=1
Step3: end=N
Step4: while start<=end do
Step5: middle= (start+end)/2
Step6: if (List[middle] < Target) then
Step7: start = middle + 1
Step8: pos=start
Step9: While (thread_var<3) do
Step10: call repaint()
// It moves searching element through specified list
//until a match is found
Step11: End While
Step12: End if
Step13: if (List[middle] > Target) then
Step14: end = middle - 1;
Step15: pos =end;
Step16: call repaint()
// It moves searching element through specified list
//until a match is found
Step17: End if
Step18: if (List[middle] =Target) then
Step19: Stop the program
Step20: End if
Step21: End while
Step22: calls ct.d1()//function that stops the timer
    
```

The Binary search option is chosen from the given list as in Fig.4.

Fig. 4 Binary search- Choosing the algorithm

The program starts and consecutively the timer is also started using the function *ct.d()*. The value 1 is stored in variable *start* and *N* in variable *end*. It finds the *middle* value using the formula $middle = (start + end)/2$. It compares the *middle* element with the *Target*. When the *Target* is greater than the *middle* element, it starts searching the upper half by assigning $start=middle+1$ and storing the start value in variable *pos* and *repaint()* function is called to move the *Target* element to the first position of the upper half as shown in Fig.5.

Fig. 5 Binary search searching the upper half

It applies the above steps for the upper half until the *Target* is found. It stops when *Target* is found as illustrated in Fig.6. When the *Target* is less than the *middle* element, the program starts searching in the lower half by assigning $end=middle-1$ and *end* value is stored in variable *pos* and *repaint()* function is called to move the *Target* element to the lower half. It applies the above steps for the lower half until the *Target* is found.

When *Target* is equal to the *middle* element the *middle* value is stored in variable *pos* and *repaint()* function is called to place the *Target* element in middle. Then the program stops and the timer is stopped using the function *ct.d1()*. It searches only in a sorted list. When the list is unsorted, it sorts the list first and then starts searching.

Fig. 6 Binary search- Element found

C. Interpolation Search

Interpolation search is an algorithm for searching a given target value in an indexed array that has been sorted in ascending order. In each search step it calculates where in the remaining search space the target might, be based on the values at the bounds of the search space and the value of the target, usually via a linear interpolation. The value actually found at this estimated position is then compared to the target value. If it is not equal, then depending on the comparison, the remaining search space is reduced to the part before or after the estimated position.

Algorithm Interpolation Search (Target, N)

N -the number of elements in the list
pos -the position of the first element to be exchanged
pos1 -the position of the second element to be exchanged
flg -temporary variable
Target -the value to be searched
thread_var - Variable to control the movement of the labels to be exchanged

ct.d(). When the list is unsorted, it sorts the list first and then starts searching.

Fig. 7 Interpolated search- Choosing the algorithm

Step1: calls *ct.d()*//function that Starts the timer
 Step2: calls Interpolation (list, Target)
 Step3: calls *ct.d1 ()*//function that stops the clock

Interpolation (sortedArray, Target) // Returns index of //Target in sortedArray, or -1 if not found

Step1: low = 0;
 Step2: high = sortedArray.length - 1;
 Step3: while (sortedArray [low] < Target && sortedArray [high] >= Target) do
 Step4: Mid = low + ((Target - sortedArray [low]) * (high - low)) / (sortedArray[high]-sortedArray[low])
 Step5: pos=mid
 Step6: calls repaint ()
 Step7: if (sortedArray[mid] < Target) then
 Step8: low = mid + 1;
 Step9: pos=mid
 Step10: calls repaint ()
 Step11: else if (sortedArray[mid] > Target) then
 Step12: high = mid - 1;
 Step13: pos=mid
 Step14: calls repaint ()
 Step15: else
 Step16: pos=mid
 Step17: calls repaint ()

Target is the value to be searched. The value 0 is assigned to the variable *low* and *sortedArray.length - 1* is assigned to variable *high*. When the *sortedArray*'s first element is less than the *Target* and the last element of the *sortedArray* is greater than the *Target*, *mid* value is calculated using the formula $mid = low + ((Target - sortedArray [low]) * (high - low)) / (sortedArray[high]-sortedArray[low])$ and the *mid* value is stored in variable *pos* and the *repaint()* function is called to move the *Target* element to the position stored in variable *pos*.

When middle value is less than *Target* assign $low = mid + 1$ and *mid* value is assigned to variable *pos* and *repaint()* function is called to move the element. When middle element of *sortedArray* is greater than *Target* then assign $high = mid - 1$ and variable *pos* is assigned the *mid* value and *repaint()* function is called to move the element. When both the above conditions are not satisfied, variable *pos* is assigned the *mid* value and *repaint()* is called to move the element and a variable *flg* is set to 1. When the *flg* value is 0 and *sortedArray[low]* is equal to *Target* the *low* is assigned to variable *pos* and *repaint()* function is called as depicted in Fig.8. Otherwise variable *pos* is assigned the value 0 and then *repaint()* function is called to swap the element. Then the program stops and the timer is stopped using the function *ct.d1()*.

Step18: End While
 Step19: if (flg=0) then
 Step20: if (SortedArray [low] =Target) then
 Step21: pos=low
 Step22: calls repaint()
 Step23: Else
 Step24: pos=0
 Step25: calls repaint()
 Step26: End if

Fig. 8 Interpolated search-Element found

First the Interpolation search option is chosen from the given list as in Fig.7.The timer is started using the function

III. SORTING ALGORITHM

In sorting algorithms the user has to give how many number of inputs and the set of data. Then select the particular algorithm from the list and then the visualization of the selected algorithm is shown with the given inputs.

A. Selection sort

The algorithm works as follows:

1. Find the minimum value in the list
2. Swap it with the value in the first position
3. Repeat the steps above for remaining of the list (to the consecutive positions)

Effectively, we divide the list into two parts: the sub list of items already sorted, which we build up from left to right and is found at the beginning, and the sub list of items remaining to be sorted, occupying the remainder of the array.

Algorithm Selection Sort (List, N)

- List* -the elements to be put in order
N -the number of elements in the list
pos -the position of the first element to be exchanged
pos1 -the position of the second element to be exchanged
t -temporary variable
min -variable to store the Minimum value
thread_var - variable to control the movement of the labels to be exchanged

Step1: calls ct.d() //Starts the timer
 Step2: For i=0 to N-1 do
 Step3: min =i

Step4: For j=i+1 to N do
 Step5: if (List[j] <List [min]) then
 Step6: min=j;
 Step7: End if
 Step8: End for
 Step9: pos=i
 Step10:pos1=min
 Step11: if (min! =i)
 Step12: while (thread_var<3)
 Step13: Calls repaint () //It Exchanges the elements
 Step14: End While
 Step15: End If
 Step16: t =List [i]
 Step17: List [i] = List [min]

Step18: List [min] =t
 Step19: thread_var =0
 Step20: End For
 Step21: calls ct.d1()//function that stops the timer

The algorithm starts by selecting the selection sort option from the list as in Fig.9 and the timer is started using the function *ct.d()*.

Fig. 9 Selection sort- Choosing the algorithm

From the first element to the last element, find the smallest element and its position is assigned to the variable *min*. Variable *pos* is assigned the value *i* that represent the position in the array starting from 1 and variable *pos1* is assigned the value *min*. Then *repaint()* function is called to swap the values in the positions given in variable *pos* and *pos1* as illustrated in Fig.10.

Fig.10 Selection sort- Performing swapping

The process continues until the *List* is sorted. The sorted *List* is shown in Fig.11 and the timer is stopped using the function *ct.d1()*.

Fig. 11 Selection sort- Sorting process completed

B. Bubble sort

The bubble sort algorithm makes number of passes through the list of elements. On each pass it compares adjacent element values. If they are out of order, they are swapped. We start each of the passes at the beginning of the list. On first pass, once the algorithm reaches the largest element, it will be swapped with all of the remaining elements, moving it to the end of the list. The second pass will move the second largest element down the list until it is in the second to last location. The process continues with each additional pass moving one more of the larger values down in the list. If on any pass there are no swaps, all of the elements are now in order and the algorithm can stop.

Algorithm Bubble Sort (List, N)

- List* -the elements to be put in order
- N* -the number of elements in the list
- pos* -the position of the first element to be exchanged
- pos1* -the position of the second element to be exchanged
- t* -temporary variable
- thread_var* -Variable to control the movement of the labels to be exchanged

- Step1: calls `ct.d()` //function to start the timer
- Step2: For $i=N-1$ to 0 Step -1 do
- Step3: For $j=0$ to i do
- Step4: if $(List[j]>List[j+1])$ then
- Step5: $pos=j$
- Step6: $pos1=j+1$
- Step7: while $(thread_var<3)$
- Step8: Calls `repaint()` //It Exchanges the elements
- Step9: End While

- Step10: $t=List[j]$
- Step11: $List[j]=List[j+1]$
- Step12: $List[j+1]=t$
- Step13: $thread_var=0$
- Step14: End if
- Step15: End for j
- Step16: End for i
- Step17: calls `ct.d1()`//function that stops the timer

Fig.12 depicts choosing the bubble sort algorithm from the given list. The program starts and the timer is started using the function `ct.d()`.

Fig.12 Bubble sort- Choosing the algorithm

The bubble sort algorithm makes $N-1$ number of passes through the *List* of elements where N is the number of input values. On each pass it compares adjacent element value. If they are out of order their position are stored in variables *pos* and *pos1* and `repaint()` function is called to swap the elements in the two positions as in Fig.13.

Fig.13 Bubble sort- Performing swapping

The program stops after the $N-1$ number of passes and the *List* is sorted as given in Fig.14. The timer is stopped using the function `ct.d1()`.

Fig.14 Bubble sort- Sorting process completed

C. Shell Sort

Shell sort was developed by Donald L. Shell. It begins by dividing the full list of values as a set of interleaved sub lists. On the first pass, it divides the list into two sub lists. On the second pass, it could be further divided into sub lists. The size of the set to be sorted gets smaller with each pass through the list, until the sub list's length become 1. As the size of the set decreases, the number of sets to be sorted increases.

Algorithm Shell Sort (List, N)

- List* -the elements to be put in order
- N* -the number of elements in the list
- pos* -the position of the first element to be exchanged
- pos1* -the position of the second element to be exchanged
- h* -variable to divide the list
- v* -variable to store the list element, to compare
- thread_var* - variable to control the movement of the labels to be exchanged

- Step1: calls `ct.d()`//function that starts the timer
- Step2: `h=len`
- Step3: `do`
- Step4: `h=h\2`
- Step5: `for i=h to n-1 do`
- Step6: `v=List[i]`
- Step7: `j=i`
- Step8: `while ((j>=h) && (list [j-h]>v)) do`
- Step9: `pos=j`
- Step10: `pos1=j-h`
- Step11: `while (thread_var<3)`
- Step12: Calls `repaint ()` //It Exchanges the elements
- Step13: `End While`

- Step14: `List[j] =List [j-h]`
- Step15: `j=j-h`
- Step16: `End While`
- Step17: `List[j] =v`
- Step18: `thread_var=0`
- Step19: `End For`
- Step20: `End while (h>1)`
- Step21: calls `ct.d()`//function that stops the timer

The shell sort algorithm begins after choosing the shell sort option from the list and clicking the start button. Timer is started using the function `ct.d()`. The *List* is divided into two sub list. After dividing the *List* into two the first element of both the sub list are compared. If they are out of order their index value in the array is stored in variables *pos* and *pos1* respectively and the *repaint()* function is called to swap the element as depicted in Fig.15.

Fig.15 Shell sort- Performing swapping

Similarly the consecutive elements are compared. The sub list are further sub divided and above procedure is repeated. The sub lists are sub divided until the length of the sub lists become one. By repeating the above procedure the whole list is sorted. The program stops after displaying the sorted list as given in Fig.16. The timer is stopped by calling the function `ct.d()`.

Fig.16 Shell sort- Sorting Completed

IV. RESULT ANALYSIS

A. Analysis of Searching Algorithms

Table I depicts the comparison of searching algorithms with average values. In searching algorithms, number of inputs are 8. Its average runtime is given in seconds. From analyzing Fig.17, we came to know that both the interpolation and binary search would be time consuming rather than sequential search. This is due to sorting the data before searching the elements. But basically an interpolation search will be less time consuming, secondly binary search will be less time consuming one while entering a sorted list as input to these algorithms. Sequential search does not need a sorted list for searching.

TABLE I COMPARISON OF SEARCHING ALGORITHMS-WITH AVERAGE VALUES

No. of Inputs	Sequential Searching in Sec.	Binary Searching in Sec.	Interpolation Searching in Sec.
0	0	0	0
1	1.3	1.3	1.3
2	1.9	3.1	3.8
3	2.6	7.8	7.7
4	3.2	23.2	23.7
5	4.3	27	28.1
6	6.4	32.3	34.2
7	8	51.2	55
8	9.6	60.8	61.4

Fig.17 Comparison of searching algorithms-with average values

B. Analysis of Sorting Algorithms

Table II illustrates the comparison between the sorting algorithms with average values. sorting algorithms are analyzed with 8 input values. Its average runtime is given in seconds. From analyzing Fig. 18, we came to know that Selection sort is less time consuming when compared to Bubble and shell sort. Among the three sorting algorithms Bubble sort will be the most time consuming algorithm. On bubble sort each time adjacent elements are compared and swapped when needed. This process will be repeated from the beginning of the array until all the elements are sorted. Therefore Bubble sort will be the most time consuming algorithm.

TABLE II COMPARISON OF SORTING ALGORITHMS-WITH AVERAGE VALUES

No. of Inputs	Selection Sorting in Sec.	Bubble Sorting in Sec.	Shell Sorting in Sec.
0	0	0	0
1	0	0	0
2	2.8	2.8	2.8
3	5.8	6.7	6.7
4	7.6	13.4	9.6
5	9.6	25	13.4
6	16.3	35.5	20.1
7	16.8	40.3	25
8	17.3	55.7	30.8

AVERAGE VALUES

Fig.18 Comparison of searching algorithms-with average values

V. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE ENHANCEMENT

This system is implemented for visualizing some of the searching and sorting algorithms. This is a helpful tool for all kinds of learners/scholars to easily understand the implicit sequences of algorithm. Here the users are allowed to select the options, either searching or sorting. Then they are allowed to give input and they can select the algorithms from the list and the algorithm is explained visually.

In future to enhance and continue this project, the system may include more algorithms for searching and sorting. Visualization can also be done for other kinds of algorithms. Voice can further be included to the system, to give more interaction for the end users.

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